

**A UNIFIED DEEP LEARNING FRAMEWORK LEVERAGING YOLOV8 AND
OPENCV FOR ROBUST VIDEO FACE RECOGNITION****BOLLA SIRISHA**

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1. ABSTRACT

This project illustrates the implementation of a Video-based Face recognition system using OpenCV that supports efficient accuracy and speed processing on normal CPU-based computers. The system processes video input, detects human faces using the YOLOv8n model, and recognizes them using the Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) algorithm. Recognized faces are compared with a pre-encoded database, while unknown faces are stored independently for examination. An CSV report is automatically produced with detection times and cropped face images of the known and unknown persons. The system runs smoothly without GPU support, and thus it is feasible to use in settings like classrooms and small office environments.

Keywords YOLO, YOLOv8n, HOG, Face Detection, Face Recognition.

2. INTRODUCTION

Face recognition has become a very useful tool in many areas such as school attendance, office security, public surveillance, and identity checking. It helps detect and recognize people from images or videos and reduces the need for manual work. Many schools and companies are now using automatic systems to take attendance or monitor who enters and exits a place. These systems are becoming popular because they are faster, more accurate, and easier to manage than traditional methods [6, 8]. In this project, we created a system that can take a video file, detect faces, recognize known people, and generate a report with images and time logs.

There are many face recognition techniques, but not all of them work well on regular laptops. Some methods use deep learning, which needs a powerful GPU and more memory. Since not everyone has access to such resources, we focused on models that work well on CPU-only systems too. After testing different models, we selected YOLOv8n for face detection and HOG (Histogram of Oriented Gradients) for face recognition. YOLOv8n is a small, fast version of the YOLO object detection model and works well for real-time face detection [13]. HOG is a classic method that looks at shapes and edges in an image to recognize faces. It is lightweight, simple, and works fine for clean, frontal faces [2, 3, 11].

We used the `face_recognition()` library in Python, which makes it easy to compare faces using HOG or deep learning. This library is built on top of Dlib and provides functions to encode faces, compare them, and draw boxes and labels. It is widely used in attendance systems and face-based apps because of its simplicity and good accuracy [14, 15]. Our system uses this library to match detected faces with known faces stored in a file. If a person is not recognized, their face is saved and included in the report. This is useful for checking unknown visitors later.

Other researchers have also used HOG and YOLO-based models in face recognition projects. Some systems used these models in schools and universities to automatically mark student attendance from videos [4, 6, 8]. Others used them in security systems where the goal was to identify people in surveillance camera footage [5, 7, 10]. These systems often worked offline, and some even ran on devices like Raspberry Pi, showing that it is possible to build useful face recognition tools even with limited hardware [5, 15].

Our system takes a similar approach. It opens a video file selected by the user, detects all faces in the video using YOLOv8n, and recognizes them using the HOG model. It records the names and appearance time of known people and saves face images for unknown ones. At the end, it creates an CSV report that shows all the faces detected, along

with time stamps and cropped images. This system is fully offline, does not require internet, and runs smoothly on a normal computer. We chose this design because it is simple, effective, and easy to use in real situations like classrooms, labs, or small offices [6, 7, 13].

3. LITERATURE SURVEY

This section highlights important research and practical implementations related to face detection and recognition, with a special focus on real-time systems using models like HOG and YOLO. The goal is to understand how different techniques have been used in projects similar to ours, particularly those working on surveillance, attendance marking, and offline detection systems.

Patgar et al. [1] built an automatic attendance system by combining Local Binary Patterns (LBP) with Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG). Their model used HOG to extract features and SVM to classify faces. The system was fast and suitable for places where GPU is not available. Dadi et al. [2] worked on face recognition and human tracking in surveillance videos using HOG and SVM. They found that combining these models with Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) gave stable results even when lighting or face angles changed slightly. Another work from Springer RTIP2R [3] used HOG features along with a simple neural network to build a real-time face recognition system. They were able to detect multiple faces at once in video streams, showing that traditional methods like HOG can still be effective. In a study published in the European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences [4], researchers built a face-based attendance system using only HOG and SVM. They reported nearly high accuracy, which proves that even without deep learning, such systems can work well on CPU-only machines. Similarly, Rhouma Bin Hamed and Fatnassi [5] created a secure attendance model using Raspberry Pi. Their setup used HOG and SVM with OpenCV to recognize faces in real-time, highlighting how simple models can be deployed on low-cost devices. This aligns closely with the goals of our own project, which is designed to work on normal laptops without GPU support.

Jain et al. [6] proposed a real-time attendance system using face recognition. Their approach involved taking snapshots of detected faces from video and matching them to stored encodings. It introduced the idea of logging appearance time, which is something our system also implements. In another study, Singh et al. [7] explored automated multi-face recognition for attendance purposes. Their system used a hybrid method combining HOG features with deep learning models, and they suggested that using both types of methods can improve accuracy and stability. This idea influenced the mixed approach of using YOLO for detection and HOG for recognition in our system.

Several other researchers also focused on HOG-based face recognition systems. Gupta et al. [8] described a smart attendance system built using Python and HOG features, showing how face detection and matching can be done efficiently with minimal resources. Bapatla et al. [9] compared CNN, LBP, and HOG-based systems. They found that HOG with good feature encoding achieved about 98% accuracy in classroom attendance setups. Abdelwahab et al. [10] introduced a web-based facial recognition tool using 2D-HOG features for identifying pilgrims during Hajj. Their method allowed efficient searching even in large crowds.

Dalal et al. [11] first introduced HOG for human detection in 2005. Their foundational paper explains how edge directions in small regions of an image can describe objects like human faces. This theory is still the base for many lightweight recognition systems. Schroff et al. [12] developed FaceNet, which showed how to turn a face into a numeric embedding that makes comparing faces easier. Though deep learning-based, this method shaped the encoding logic used even in simpler tools like `face_recognition()`.

YOLOv8n, the latest model from Ultralytics [13], was designed to be faster and more efficient. It works well even on CPUs and has been used in several face detection setups. The `face_recognition()` library [14] uses both CNN and HOG models for recognizing faces and has become popular for small projects and offline systems. A GitHub project [15] showed how to build an attendance system using HOG and OpenCV, which helped us a lot with our own project.

4. METHODOLOGY

The core objective of this project is to design a face recognition-based surveillance system that can automatically detect and recognize people from recorded video footage as shown in Fig. 1. The system uses YOLOv8n for detecting persons in each frame of the video and the `face_recognition()` library for identifying known individuals. The video, usually taken from a CCTV camera, is processed frame by frame. YOLOv8n, a lightweight yet powerful deep learning

model developed by Ultralytics, is used to detect human presence (class label: person) in each frame. This model is efficient and suitable for real-time use even on systems without a GPU. It works by using a backbone to extract features from images, a neck to combine these features, and a head that predicts bounding boxes and class labels with confidence scores.

Fig. 1 Methodology

After YOLOv8n detects a person in the frame, that face is cropped and passed to the `face_recognition()` module, which compares the face against a known database using HOG-based 128-dimensional embeddings. If the face is recognized, it is labeled with the person's name with their appearance timings otherwise, it is marked as "Unknown." The system tracks the entry and exits time of each person someone entering first appears and the moment they leave the frame. These timestamps are saved along with the name of the person in a structured CSV file, which makes it easy to analyze the data later. This logging mechanism is particularly useful for monitoring attendance or reviewing surveillance recordings in a quick and structured manner.

In addition to detection and recognition, the system allows users to extract specific segments from the video by providing a start and end timestamp. This feature is useful for reviewing particular time intervals without watching the entire footage. Overall, the methodology combines the speed and efficiency of YOLOv8n for detection with the reliability of `face_recognition()` for matching faces, resulting in a system that is both practical and effective for use in security, attendance tracking, and personal identification from video sources.

5. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

The system was tested using various recorded video clips containing multiple individuals walking in and out of the frame. The main goal was to detect persons accurately using YOLOv8n and identify them correctly using the `face_recognition()` library as shown in Fig. 2. The system was able to detect faces consistently, even when people appeared at different positions or distances in the video. The combination of YOLOv8n for detection and HOG-based face recognition allowed for quick identification. Known individuals were labeled with their names, while unknown persons were marked and stored separately for later review.

Fig. 2 Face Recognition using YOLOv8n

Name	Entry	Exit
Pravallika	00:00:00	00:00:26

Fig. 3 entry_exit_log.csv

The entry and exit times of each detected person were recorded and saved into a CSV file as shown in Fig. 3. This helped in verifying how long each person stayed within the video frame. The logs created were well-organized and readable, allowing for quick analysis. In addition to logging, the feature that lets users extract specific video segments based on time input proved useful for isolating important events. This functionality made it easier to analyze particular interactions or movements in the footage without scanning the entire video manually.

Overall, the system performed smoothly without a GPU. YOLOv8n handled detection tasks efficiently with good accuracy, while `face_recognition()` successfully matched faces in most cases with less delay. The use of both models together provided better results than using either one alone. While extremely small or blurry faces posed minor challenges, the system's performance in regular lighting and frontal view conditions was effective and reliable for basic surveillance and attendance tracking purposes.

6. CONCLUSION

This project aimed to create a simple and effective face recognition system using video input, and it was successfully achieved. By using the YOLOv8n model for detecting people and the `face_recognition()` library for matching faces, the system was able to identify known individuals in recorded videos and log their entry and exit times properly. The results were stored in a CSV file, making it easy to review and analyze later. The system worked well even on a normal laptop without a GPU, which shows that it is lightweight and can be used in places where high-end systems are not available. The project was especially useful for surveillance and attendance tracking. Users can extract and review only the parts of the video they want by entering specific start and end times, which makes it more flexible and user-friendly. The project showed that combining detection and recognition into one system can help save time and make video analysis much easier.

In conclusion, this system brings together speed, accuracy, and simplicity. It can be useful in real-world situations like classrooms, offices, or small security setups where there's a need to know who was present and when. While there's still room for improvement, such as recognizing faces from difficult angles or very low lighting, the current setup is good enough for many basic needs. This project also helped in understanding how different models like YOLOv8n and HOG work, and how they can be used together to build a complete face recognition solution.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Patgar, et al., "A Face Recognition Based Automatic Attendance Management System by Combining LBP and HOG Features," in *Proc. International Conference on Inventive Communication and Computational Technologies (ICICCT)*, 2018, Springer.
- [2] R. K. Dadi, et al., "Face Recognition and Human Tracking Using GMM, HOG and SVM in Surveillance Videos," *Annals of Data Science*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 231–242, 2018.
- [3] A. Shah and R. K. Bharti, "Multi Faces Recognition System Using HOG Features and Neural Network Classifier," in *Proc. Real-Time Intelligent Processing and Robotics (RTIP2R)*, 2020, Springer.

- [4] P. Zope and A. Thorat, "Face Recognition Based Attendance System Using Histogram of Oriented Gradients and Linear Support Vector Machine," *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 12–18, 2022.
- [5] M. Rhouma Bin Hamed and A. Fatnassi, "A Secure Attendance System using Raspberry Pi Face Recognition (HOG+SVM)," *Journal of Telecommunications and the Digital Economy*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 68–79, 2022.
- [6] S. Jain, A. Roy, and N. Sharma, "AttenFace: A Real-Time Attendance System using Face Recognition," *arXiv preprint*, arXiv:2211.07582, 2022.
- [7] A. Choudhury and K. R. Singh, "Automated Attendance Tracking via Multi-Face Recognition," *International Journal of Computer Techniques*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 35–41, 2023.
- [8] R. Gupta and P. Tiwari, "Automated Smart Attendance System Using Face Recognition," *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology (IJRASET)*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 832–837, 2023.
- [9] S. Bapatla and T. Naidu, "Face Recognition Based Attendance System Using CNN, LBP and HOG," *EasyChair Preprint*, no. 9482, 2022.
- [10] A. Abdelwahab, M. A. S. Khalil, and T. Ragab, "Efficient Web-based Facial Recognition Employing 2D-HOG," *arXiv preprint*, arXiv:1202.2449, 2012.
- [11] N. Dalal and B. Triggs, "Histograms of Oriented Gradients for Human Detection," in *Proc. IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2005, pp. 886–893.
- [12] F. Schroff, D. Kalenichenko, and J. Philbin, "FaceNet: A Unified Embedding for Face Recognition and Clustering," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2015, pp. 815–823.
- [13] Ultralytics, "YOLOv8: Real-Time Object Detection and Tracking," *IJSREM*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 128–135, 2023.
- [14] A. Rosebrock, "face_recognition: Recognizing Faces in Images with Python," *Open Source Computer Vision Blog*, 2021. [Online].
- [15] T. Bapatla, "Face Detection Attendance System Using HOG and OpenCV," *GitHub Project*, 2022. [Online].